

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

Quality Assurance Plan - final release
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D1.6 QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN FINAL RELEASE

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Abstract	This document presents the final release of the Quality Assurance Plan, reflecting the project’s quality management approach as updated and consolidated at the end of the implementation period. It outlines how the key aspects of the project have been managed, monitored, and controlled, providing an overview of the quality assurance processes applied throughout the project lifecycle. The plan summarizes the measures taken to ensure compliance with defined standards in areas such as schedule, cost, risk, communication, and deliverable quality, and integrates lessons learned and improvements identified during implementation to

	support future replication or sustainability efforts.
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3	EUROPEAN BUSINESS ANGELS NETWORK	EBAN	BE
4	ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS	ATHENA/ CORALLIA	EL
5	KLIYNTEH BULGARIA	CLEANTECH BG	BG
6	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	F6S	IE
7	LUISS LIBERA UNIVERSITÀ INTERNAZIONALE DEGLI STUDI SOCIALI GUIDO CARLI	LUISS	IT
8	PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS	UTH	EL

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The concept of ENTREPRENEDU is focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between different regions of the European Union that is causing unbalanced business activities and fewer job opportunities in less developed entrepreneurial ecosystems. In other words, the ENTREPRENEDU project aims to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for European education. To this end, the project seeks to improve the quality and outreach of both innovation and educational ecosystems, implementing a high replicable and scalable Venture Building Program for youth, an educational model for the European entrepreneurial ecosystems developed via a series of 3 Hackathons, developed at regional level, supporting concepts and ideas to become concrete solutions, thus enhancing cooperation between businesses and education providers.

The final release of the Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) of ENTREPRENEDU describes how the project management team implemented its quality policy. The elaboration of the QAP allowed ENTREPRENEDU partners to define the organisational structure, responsibilities, procedures, processes, and resources needed to implement quality management.

The present release QAP is the report that describes the procedures and processes that were implemented during the project to ensure that the project satisfied the needs for which it was undertaken. It includes all the activities of the overall management function that determined the quality policy, objectives, and responsibilities and implemented them by means such as quality planning, quality control, quality assurance, and quality improvement, within the quality system.

Projects such as ENTREPRENEDU usually generate large sets of activities and involve several parties in their implementation. With this QAP ENTREPRENEDU consortium aims at providing an analysis of the main elements of the quality management policy that were used in the project and by the partners with regard to the project research development.

This updated report covers a broad range of aspects related to ENTREPRENEDU quality management, thanks to the combination of the first version and an intermediary internal check. Benefits of creating a QAP included: clearly defining roles, responsibilities, processes and activities; increasing probability that projects will complete on-time, within budget, and with high degree of quality; ensuring understanding of what was agreed upon; helping project teams identify and plan for

how project activities will be managed (budget, quality, schedule, etc.). The intended audience of the final release of the ENTREPRENEDU QAP consists of members of the ENTREPRENEDU consortium and the EC Project Adviser.

The first two sections of the QAP offer an introduction and an overview of the procedures and processes implemented to grant a high level quality assurance. Section 3 introduces quality management while section 4 (project organisation) follows with the project schedule, the description of the project budget, and risk management. The last 4 sections focus on: project communication, project reporting as well as on change management.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
CA	CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT
DMP	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
DoA	DESCRIPTION OF ACTION
Dx.y.	DELIVERABLE Y OF WORK PACKAGE X
EC	EUROPEAN COMMISSION
EU	EUROPEAN UNION
GA	GRANT AGREEMENT
GDPR	GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION
G.O.	GENERAL OBJECTIVE
IPR	INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS
MIM	MUTUAL INSURANCE MECHANISM
MoU	MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
Mxy	PROJECT MONTH XY
PA	PROJECT ADVISER
PC	PROJECT COORDINATOR
PM	PROJECT MANAGER
QAP	QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN
SMEs	SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES
TC	TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

TRL	TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL
WP	WORK PACKAGE
WPL	WORK PACKAGE LEADER

1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 1.6 details the updated Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) of the ENTREPRENEDU project. The purpose of this document is to provide a documented plan for the management and control of the organisational, developmental, and supporting processes that were necessary to the assurance of the quality from the successful implementation of the ENTREPRENEDU project. It outlines the goals and objectives and organisational structure; defines the responsibilities and roles of project participants; identifies the interactions among project partners; and specifies the general procedures and management tools that are implemented to ensure effective quality management and successful project completion. The development of the QAP was an evolving process: the QAP was updated and revised as needed. Revisions to the QAP included periodic updates to the plan, especially related to project budget, schedule, and risks. The Project Coordinator was responsible for the maintenance of and revisions to the QAP. The project quality management process and procedures included in this QAP are based on the Project Management Body of Knowledge, the PMBOK® Guide, 5th Edition (Rose, 2013), published by the Project Management Institute, and are integrated with practices of modern project management tailored to the needs of the present project. The ENTREPRENEDU project employed a standard project quality management approach based on documented timelines, regular communications, active follow up, and formal quality control and risk mitigation processes. To support its project quality management approach, the ENTREPRENEDU project used cloud-shared, revision history-enabled, and always synced folders (provided by Google Drive service) and a set of dedicated conference calls as well as in person meetings. The combination of these solutions provided the team with facilities for sharing and managing of documents, managing work packages and related tasks, tracking progress against task deliverables, scheduling meetings and discussions, and generally ensuring that the distributed project team can pro-actively collaborate to meet project requirements. In order to ensure that regular progress reports were produced on time by deliverable leaders, FEA with the support of F6S created procedures and templates. These procedures were finalised to assure that actual resource consumption was tracked against plan, that any deviations from the plan were quickly surfaced, and appropriate risk mitigation actions were taken. To facilitate on-going reporting activities and project team work, email lists were created and conference calling facilities were established. In addition, a project website was developed to provide not only internal communications capabilities for the ENTREPRENEDU team, but to support the team's dissemination and exploitation

activities. Finally, formal quality control and risk management processes were established so that project deliverables met the operational criteria so that any deviations from plan were properly addressed.

2 OVERVIEW OF ENTREPRENEDU PROJECT

ENTREPRENEDU focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between different regions of the European Union that is causing unbalanced business activities and fewer job opportunities in less developed entrepreneurial ecosystems. ENTREPRENEDU aimed to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for European education via a series of three hackathons taking place in Italy, Greece, and Bulgaria during the project development with the objective of selecting at the end of each hackathon the best 4 entrepreneurial ideas entered the Business Acceleration programme as proposed by the project partners. For the Bulgarian Hackathon, 5 teams were selected in the end. Besides these activities, ENTREPRENEDU created a Venture Building Programme that was tested on over 200 students and subsequently fine-tuned for exploitation purposes.

2.1 PROJECT PURPOSES AND OBJECTIVES

The project aimed to improve the quality and outreach of both innovation and educational ecosystems, implementing a Venture Building program for youth, thus enhancing cooperation between businesses and education providers.

Therefore, the General Objective (G.O.) of the project ENTREPRENEDU was creating a highly replicable and scalable educational model for both businesses and educational systems via a series of 3 Hackathons, developed at regional level, supporting developed concepts and ideas (TRL2) to become concrete solutions (TRL5). The program was validated at the end of the project in 3 different educational entities (2 universities and the "Aspekti" Vocational Training Center of Cleantech Bulgaria). As a consequence, ENTREPRENEDU had the following specific objectives:

- Analysing qualitatively and quantitatively the needs of low and moderate innovative regions in terms of entrepreneurial know-how in education and best case scenarios;

- Assessing and improving, collaboration between developed and less developed innovation ecosystems, quality, capacity, competitiveness, comprehensiveness and outreach of business acceleration services;
- Creating an educational program to strengthen business knowledge and skills, as well as entrepreneurship, in less and moderate innovative regions;
- Bringing together regional high-potential start-ups, youth, and business stakeholders to give an impulse to improve the entrepreneurial systems in the regions targeted by the project;
- Evaluating the sustainability of the ENTREPRENEDU methodology and solutions.

ENTREPRENEDU aimed at increasing the development of know-how and new entrepreneurs by strengthening the connection between the education system and businesses and including them in collaborative processes, supporting the growth of less developed innovation ecosystems, raising their start-ups and SMEs investors attractiveness and giving them the know – how and knowledge to reach the market:

Figure 1: Graphic representation of the ENTREPRENEDU project

2.2 PROJECT MILESTONES

For a correct tracking of progress, the ENTREPRENEDU project adopted a work plan with seven Milestones as reported in the table below:

Table 1: ENTREPRENEDU milestones table

Milestones					
Grant Preparation (Milestones screen)					
Milestone No	Milestone Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
1	ENTREPRENEDU kick-off	WP1	1-FEA	Minutes of Meeting of the kick-off.	1
2	Context analysis	WP2	7-LUISS	Public guideline related to needs analysis.	6
3	Cross-fertilisation analysis	WP3	4-ATHENA/CORALLIA	Hackathons implementation report.	22
4	Business Acceleration	WP4	2-Fraunhofer	Mentoring modules implemented	23
5	Venture Building programme	WP5	3-EBAN	Educational model implemented and validated.	30
6	Exploitation strategy	WP6	5-CLEANTECH BG	Business plan on the ENTREPRENEDU model.	30
7	Dissemination and communication strategy	WP7	6-F6S	Dissemination and communication plan.	30

2.3 PROJECT DELIVERABLES

A set of deliverables in chronological order of delivery is identified in the table below as a concrete output of the project's activities implementation:

Cod.	Deliverable	Date	Month	WP	Partner
D1.1	Kick-off Minutes	14-02-2023	1	WP1	1 - FEA
D7.1	Dissemination and communication plan	14-03-2023	2	WP7	6 - F6S
D1.2	Data Management Plan	14-04-2023	3	WP1	1 - FEA
D1.3	Quality Assurance Plan	14-04-2023	3	WP1	1 - FEA
D2.1	Inventory of the success cases and go-to-business scenario	14-05-2023	4	WP2	7 - LUISS
D3.1	Hackathon Handbook Template	14-06-2023	5	WP3	4 - ATHENA/CORALLIA
D2.2	Public guideline on specific needs for low moderate innovation regions	14-07-2023	6	WP2	7 - LUISS
D4.1	Mentoring modules	14-08-2023	7	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer

D4.3	Feedback collection	14-08-2023	7	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D1.4	Internal progress report	14-01-2024	12	WP1	1 - FEA
D4.2	Report on mentoring activities	14-03-2024	14	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D4.4	Mentoring modules - final release	14-08-2024	19	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D4.5	Report on mentoring activities - final release	14-08-2024	19	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D5.1	Call for students	14-08-2024	19	WP5	3 - EBAN
D4.6	Feedback collection - final release	14-09-2024	20	WP4	2 - Fraunhofer
D5.2	Syllabus of the Venture Building course	14-09-2024	20	WP5	3 - EBAN
D5.3	Venture Building course Teaching Material	14-09-2024	20	WP5	3 - EBAN
D3.2	Hackathons implementation report	14-11-2024	22	WP3	4 - ATHENA/CORALLIA
D5.4	Fine-tuning survey on the venture building program and related Fellowship	14-02-2025	25	WP5	3 - EBAN
D7.2	Dissemination and communication plan - final release	14-02-2025	25	WP7	6 - F6S
D6.1	Business plan on ENTREPRENEDU model	14-05-2025	28	WP6	5 - CLEANTECH BG
D6.2	Publication of 3 guidelines on the ENTREPRENEDU standard operating procedures	14-05-2025	28	WP6	5 - CLEANTECH BG
D1.5	Data Management Plan - final release	14-07-2025	30	WP1	1 - FEA
D1.6	Quality Assurance Plan - final release	14-07-2025	30	WP1	1 - FEA
D6.3	3 MoUs signed with other EU initiatives and/or educational entities	14-07-2025	30	WP6	5 - CLEANTECH BG

3 QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Quality management is the process of defining the strategy and methods the project will deploy to ensure the project's deliverables are of acceptable quality before they are delivered. Quality management addresses all the issues related to quality assurance, self-assessment and any ethical issues. All ethical issues are specifically addressed in deliverable D1.2 (Data Management Plan) and its updated version D1.5 (Data Management Plan - Final Release).

Project Quality management was fundamental to the success of the project, and the project adopted a methodology with three separated processes:

- *Quality Planning* which identified the quality standards relevant to the project and determined how to satisfy them;

- *Quality assurance* which was the execution of processes and procedures to ensure the achievement of quality, to assure that the project satisfied the needs for which it was undertaken;
- *Quality control* which verified and assessed the achievement/product; it was concerned with the operational activities and techniques that were used to fulfil the requirements of quality.

Quality management was the responsibility of the Project Coordinator (PC), who ensured quality of the project management and, consequently, of all deliverables, and provided measurement criteria to verify the success of the project.

The Work Plan of the ENTREPRENEDU project describes milestones and the acceptance criteria for each phase of the project. Assessing adherence to these baseline conditions provided the method for evaluating both the project and its services.

Quality organisation was under the responsibility of the PC. The PC was supported by the Project Manager (PM) in the definition and in the execution of the control activities planned or considered useful during the ENTREPRENEDU project. The PC also received support, advice, and help at several levels:

- from Work Package leaders in several quality functions related to the delivery process. Activities leaders were fully responsible for scientific and technical quality check of all deliverables.
- from the European Commission. The European Commission, through the Project Adviser, provided advice on any quality issue related to the project when necessary and requested. The Work Package Leaders also could request advice from the Project Officer on quality issues whenever necessary, usually communicating through the PC.

The PC was in charge of ensuring that deliverables to be submitted were structured, harmonised, and organised to ensure that they were timely, exhaustive, clear, and effective.

3.1 DOCUMENT PRODUCTION PROCESS

During the project, many kinds of documents were produced. It was crucial to define common formats of documents, and uniform rules of their description, responsibilities, revision plans, and revision procedures.

When producing any document to be distributed to at least one other partner of the project, each contributor was to apply the rules below, in particular:

- Produce the document in an electronic file with the same name as the File Name;
- Use the English language;
- Use the appropriate template;

Deliverables structure:

- A front page with general data about the document and the ENTREPRENEDU logo
- Version history
- A table of contents
- An Executive summary
- An introduction including the scope of the document
- Sections constituting the body of the document
- Possible Annexes
- Page numbering

The different actors involved in the production of documents were:

- Document leader: was the deliverable responsible as indicated in the deliverable list
- Other contributors: were the partners/beneficiaries involved in the activities related to the Deliverable
- Reviewers: representatives of partner organisations who review and provide feedback on the document
- WP/Task leader
- Project Coordinator (PC)

The document leader was the person in charge of the production of a document. The production rules and guidelines and the document rules had to be applied under their responsibility.

3.2 DELIVERABLES MONITORING AND CONTROL

The monitoring process was to envisage in advance possible problems connected to the development of tasks and the production of deliverables. To facilitate communicating progress on each deliverable, each WP Leader (WPL) reported progress and issues on deliverable production and on the work package implementation during monthly meetings' calls.

Deliverables were generated under the responsibility of the WPL, who was charged with ensuring that all deliverables are prepared correctly and in time.

Each project deliverable was the target of a peer review by two reviewers before being submitted to the Commission, to guarantee that it met the objectives of the project as a whole. The limit date for reception of comments was 5 working days.

During the review, the PC checked if the deliverable met the formal requirements regarding the file format, and naming and versioning schemes. Furthermore, they monitored and maintained the review process itself.

The document leader was in charge of the update of a document after internal review. They received the comments from the reviewers, addressed all comments, and took into account the accepted ones.

The quality control process for deliverables required that the deliverable owners and reviewers ensured that the deliverables adhered to the following quality aspects:

1. the contribution of the deliverable to the WP and the overall goals of ENTREPRENEDU project was to be clearly stated;
2. the objectives of the deliverable were to be clearly expressed. Specifically, the deliverable should feature a short 1-2 paragraphs introduction that clearly states the role and duty of said document, in the scope of ENTREPRENEDU;
3. the deliverable was to be clearly related to previous and future deliverables in the WP and – if applicable – to deliverables from other WPs;
4. the relation / additions / differences to previous deliverables in the same work package (i.e., in the case the deliverable is an improved version of a previous one) were to be clearly stated;

5. the deliverable was to be a self-contained document, which can be understood without knowledge of the DoA (or previous deliverables);
6. the deliverable contents were to be consistent with its description in the DoA; if not, the deviation was to be explained;
7. the deliverable was to be cohesive and concise (typically not more than 50-60 pages);
8. the deliverable was to not contain any claims that were not proven or supported by references.

The final version of the deliverables was to be submitted to the Project Coordinator in Word and PDF formats. The PDF is the electronic format requested by the EC for the submission of all the deliverables/documents elaborated during the project. When finally approved, public deliverables were published via the project web site; the same applies for all pending deliverables at the date of this document.

In order to grant a high-quality Quality Assurance and Management Plan, the following sections provide detailed guidance on all the activities that were required for proper project coordination, implementation, and development.

4 PROJECT ORGANISATION

4.1 MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

The coordination of the ENTREPRENEDU project required special attention to the quality management of multidisciplinary activities in order to define an organisation that meets the overall ENTREPRENEDU project objectives, with the right balance between rigour and flexibility and giving room to innovation and creativity. Special attention was also to be paid to the content of each WP in order to ensure the maximum consistency and solidity in the project.

The main objective of the quality management was to ensure that all project-related tasks were performed successfully and comply with contractual requirements. The key features for successful project quality management were:

- a management organisation that is matched with the project complexity;
- efficient communications within the organisation;
- clear definition of contractual requirements and relationships;
- adequate planning and control procedures;

- comprehensive quality and risk management frameworks.

In order to achieve efficient project implementation, the structures of the Work Packages and their related tasks were defined with the aim of minimising overlap between different activities. The efficient relation among tasks and WPs in the ENTREPRENEDU work-plan allowed a clear definition of responsibilities, roles and objectives for all project resources. Within the project, each partner had a clear responsibility and lines of reporting: each task activity in a WP was led by a partner, with the task leader reporting to the work package leader, coordinating the technical work for their activity according to the project and WP objectives.

The management structure was based on the extensive experience of the partners in European funded projects and was adapted in order to meet the requirements of a project that was characterised by an ambitious activity plan and a heterogeneous consortium. The ENTREPRENEDU main elements of the project organisations were:

- A. the Project Coordinator, acting as the general manager and overseeing the technical progress of ENTREPRENEDU;
- B. the Project Manager, supporting the Project Coordinator in administrative, financial and management issues;
- C. the Work Package Leaders, responsible for successful execution of the work packages;
- D. the Steering Committee, chaired by the Coordinator and one senior representative of each partner, was the decision-making body of the consortium;
- E. the Technical Committee, responsible for the day-by-day technical project management activities, was constituted by the Project Coordinator and the WP leaders.

4.2 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

The ENTREPRENEDU project was implemented through the concerted efforts of various organisations and responsible parties, who worked together as an integrated team providing multiple levels of oversight to ensure a successful outcome for the project. This subsection describes the responsibilities for the main roles and presents the persons appointed to cover the specific roles.

- Role: Project Coordinator (PC)

Appointed Person: Eleonora Lombardi (FEA)

Main Responsibilities: The PC was the primary responsible for the ENTREPRENEDU project and acted as the intermediary between the Consortium and the European Commission. They were also responsible for the overall coordination of the project execution, and worked on the day-to-day management of the project in collaboration with the Project Manager. In particular, the Project Coordinator was responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations;
- collecting, reviewing, and submitting information on the progress of the project, reports, and other deliverables to the EC;
- preparing the meetings, proposing decisions, and preparing the agenda of Project Management Board meetings, chairing the meetings, and monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings;
- transmitting promptly documents and information connected with the Project;
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents which are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.

The Project Coordinator was assisted in their role and responsibilities by the Project Manager.

- Role: Project Manager (PM)

Appointed Person: Valerio Roscani (FEA)

Main Responsibilities: The PM was responsible for overseeing the Administrative and Financial Management of the project, managing advance payments, transferring the sums allocated among the contractors as per budget, and record-keeping of EC payments allocated/paid to the contractors. The PM also supported the PC in making sure that the project was managed using the highest standards and procedures in compliance with the recognised international standards for project management set by the Project Management Institute (PMI). They were responsible for ensuring that all key deliverables were met within time, cost, and performance constraints, and that they adhered to proper quality control mechanisms and standards. The PM was to ensure that all assigned resources were effectively and efficiently utilised and that the project was properly resourced with both internal and external resources. They were in charge of: regular status reports and updates to executives; ensuring that all partners are kept informed and up-to-date as to what their responsibilities are in

relation to the project; budget tracking actual against estimated; assistance to the Project Coordinator in the day-to-day management of the Project.

- Role: Work Package Leader (WPL)

Appointed Persons: Valerio Roscani (FEA), Henry Nicolai (Fraunhofer IPK), Natalia Costanzo (EBAN), Ina Stoyanova(CTBG), Daniel Silva (F6S), Christian Lechner (LUISS), Nektaria Berikou (Corallia).

Main Responsibilities: Each WPL was responsible for the planning, progress control, quality management, and the successful completion of their WP and of the interactions with the other WPs according to the work plan. Their activities included:

- keeping work package on track and report WP status to the PC;
- Planning and distributing among WP partners actions transmitted by the PC and monitoring their execution;
- supervising the work of the WP team, identifying problems and risks, and, when necessary, proposing revisions of the WP plan.

- Role: Steering Committee (SC)

Appointed Persons: Eleonora Lombardi (FEA), Henry Nicolai (Fraunhofer IPK), Natalia Costanzo (EBAN), Ina Stoyanova(CTBG), Daniel Silva (F6S), Christian Lechner (LUISS), Nektaria Berikou (Corallia), Achilleas Barlas (University of Thessaly).

Main Responsibilities: Each member had a vote and decisions were made by majority. It was the consortium's decision-making and arbitration board of the project. The SC supervised the development of planned activities and defined the overall project strategy, considering long-term interests of the project and fulfilment of the Grant Agreement (GA) commitments. It was responsible for: consortium's budget and financial allocation of EC's contribution among various activities, annual validation of realised expenditures according to the budget, monitoring of external risks which may impair progress towards objectives, proposing strategies and contingency plans to address those risks, any issue related to modifications and amendments of the GA and the CA (e.g., project duration extension and budget reallocation), withdrawal, inclusion or exclusion of a consortium member, conflicts within partners of the consortium for any issue contemplated in the CA.

- Role: Technical Committee (TC)

Appointed Persons: Eleonora Lombardi (FEA), Henry Nicolai (Fraunhofer IPK), Natalia Costanzo (EBAN), Ina Stoyanova(CTBG), Daniel Silva (F6S), Christian Lechner (LUISS), Nektaria Berikou (Corallia), Achilleas Barlas (University of Thessaly).

Main Responsibilities: The TC was responsible for the day-by-day technical project management activities. They: reported on progresses towards project's objectives, monitor technical progresses and achievements, took corrective measures/contingency plans, review internal work plans (especially for activities across WPs), ensured deliverables/reports are of good technical quality/timely issued, discussed about common exploitation/dissemination actions and other innovation-related activities. TC met via video/teleconference once a month, with face-to-face meetings every 6 months or more frequently if needed. In all cases, decision-making powers, voting rights of its members, majority requirements as well as convocation conditions, notices, chairmanship and other aspects are regulated in the CA to ensure the maximum efficiency and the control on project direction.

An organisation based on these roles provides a good balance between striving for a light organisational load and detailing a structure that fits with the complex of a project like ENTREPRENEDU. The table below shows the management figures and responsibilities:

Table 2: Table of management figures and their responsibilities

Management category	Responsibility	Appointed body
General Management	Overall direction and major decisions of the project; communication, control and corrective measures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project Coordinator (PC) - Work Package Leaders
Financial and day-to-day management	Supervision of deliverables preparation and submission, organisation of project meetings and reviews, control overall project expenditure, cost report collection, check and payment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project Manager (PM)
Scientific and technical management	Coordination of operative efforts on a scientific, technical, services and business related basis, responsible for scientific, technical and business decisions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project Coordinator (PC) - WP Leaders (WPL) - Technical Committee - Steering Committee
Consultancy, Exploitation,	Monitoring, consultancy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project Coordinator (PC)

Dissemination	feed-back, exploitation and dissemination of the results of the project in order to provide fundamental impact and boost the adoption of project results outside the Consortium.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP Leaders (WPL) - Technical Committee - Steering Committee
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4.3 CONSORTIUM PROCEDURES

Day-to-day scientific and management decisions were taken by the PC. Strategic decisions and major technical and operational decisions (like any reschedule of deliverables, milestones, tasks, effort) were taken by the Steering Committee, which had the highest decision-making responsibility and policy-setting power.

The Steering Committee was not to deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members were present or represented (quorum). Each member was to have one vote. Defaulting Parties could not vote. In case of conflict resolution voting, a majority of 80% was required. The PC mediated and participated in all important decisions.

Any decision could also be taken without a meeting if the PC circulated to all members a written document which was then signed by the defined majority of members. Such a document had to include the deadline for responses. Decisions were only binding once the relevant part of the minutes had been accepted.

A member who could show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of the Steering Committee could exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision. When the decision was foreseen on the original agenda, a member could veto such a decision during the meeting only. When a decision had been made on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a member could veto such a decision during the meeting and within 15 days after the draft minutes of the meeting are sent. In case of exercise of veto, the members were to make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all members. A Party could not veto decisions relating to its identification as a Defaulting Party. The Defaulting Party could not veto decisions relating to its participation and termination in the consortium or

the consequences of them. A Party requesting to leave the consortium could not veto decisions relating thereto.

The PC produced written minutes of each meeting, which were the formal record of all decisions taken. They sent draft minutes to all members within 10 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes were considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no member had sent an objection in writing to the PC with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes. The PC sent the accepted minutes to all the members of the Steering Committee.

The Steering Committee was free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out.

4.4 ISSUE MANAGEMENT

Conflict was not a significant factor since the roles of each partner were well defined, so as to avoid any misunderstandings that could have occurred later in the project. The resolution of problems and conflicts was handled systematically. Establishing a good working relationship among the project team members was a prerequisite for the quick resolution of problems and issues. Conflicts' resolution was based on the principle that any dispute was to be resolved by consent and as near the source as possible, thus, conflicts on a local sphere were managed by the people involved (e.g., a dispute between the partners engaged in a WP should be addressed by that WP team). Conflicts which could not be solved internally were taken through a "principled negotiation" process that was focused on optimising outcomes and maximising the benefits of all parties involved.

In case of conflicts arising within the consortium regarding the carrying out of the project or other matters related to the project itself, the following steps were taken:

1. The parties tried to resolve the conflict issue amicably between them.
2. If a conflict could not be resolved within the local sphere, it was raised to the PC; for conflict resolution in a technical aspect, the PC was in charge of proposing an alternative. If this was agreed, the issue was solved.
3. If this attempt failed, the question was brought to the first scheduled meeting of the SC, or in case of urgency, an ad hoc meeting of the SC was called for by the Project Coordinator, upon request of a SC member;
4. The question was discussed within the SC, and the Project Coordinator tried to solve it by consensus; the SC decided which procedure was to be followed, and

the corresponding correction measures that were to be taken. The participant that provoked the conflict declared acceptance of the procedure and the corrective measures.

Since every conflict was ultimately resolved at an earlier stage, it was not necessary to proceed with the final escalation steps. Therefore, no declaration of non-alignment was made by the Project Coordinator, and no request for contract termination was submitted. The European Commission was not involved, and no revision of the work plan was required. As a result, the voting procedure among partners foreseen in case of unresolved conflicts was not activated.

4.5 STAKEHOLDERS (INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL)

Management of stakeholders' engagement was carried out within WP2, although strong links were activated with WP6 and WP7 activities both in dissemination and communication as well as in exploitation. Stakeholders were considered key drivers to project exploitation, so their selection was done among target audience categories, with priorities given to decision makers and opinion leaders. It was mandatory to include stakeholder representatives of institutions, social communities, business actors and research excellences. The key stakeholder categories that were mapped and engaged throughout the project are summarised in the table below.

Table 3: Table representing the stakeholder categories identified for ENTREPRENEDU

ID	Description	Interest(s)	Observations
STK #1	Project partners	Active participants in the project development	Engaged
STK #2	End users	Startups and SMEs in the scaleup phase applying for ENTREPRENEDU services	Engaged
STK #3	European Commission	Project enabler, Research outcomes and their evaluation	Engaged
STK #4	Business entities	Business exploitation around ENTREPRENEDU outcomes should be designed around their needs	Engaged

STK #5	Scientific community	Scientific exploitation of achieved results	Engaged
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For each identified stakeholder category, an analysis of their interests and whether those interests were in favour or against the goals of the project was conducted by the task leader and the support of the whole consortium. For those stakeholders that it was considered appropriate, pro-active engagement plans were defined and conducted. On a regular basis, a review of the stakeholder list was done to identify new (if any) stakeholders and to assess the engagement and attitude of each stakeholder. When needed, new engagement plans were defined and launched and already existing engagement plans were modified.

5 PROJECT SCHEDULE

An overall ENTREPRENEDU high-level schedule was prepared by the PM including the different phases, duration and delivery time:

Table 4: Table representing the GANTT of ENTREPRENEDU

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	
Hackathons					H1					H2	H3																				
Mentoring																															
Venture Building Programme Validation																															
Milestones	M					M																	M	M						M	
WP1 Project Management and Coordination																															
T1.1 General Assembly meetings	GA					GA						GA										GA								GA	
T1.2 Reporting and internal communication	D1.1											D1.4																			
T1.3 Data Management				D1.2																										D1.5	
T1.4 Quality Assurance				D1.3																										D1.6	
WP2 Context analysis and stakeholders setting																															
T2.1 Success cases and go-to-business scenario				D2.1																											
T2.2 Needs identification for low and moderate innovative regions						D2.2																									
WP3 Hackathons, trainings and awareness raising initiatives																															
T3.1 Hackathons' design and implementation plan				D3.1																											
T3.2 Pre-hackathon campaign -Information sessions																															
T3.3 Launch of the Call for the Hackathons (registration, selection)																															
T3.4 Hackathons' implementation																													D3.2		
WP4 Supporting Business Acceleration																															
T4.1 Coordination and definition of mentoring activities												D4.2																			
T4.2 Elaboration and delivery of mentoring modules						D4.1																	D4.5								
T4.3 Post Hackathons interview from participants and stakeholders						D4.3																	D4.4								
WP5 Venture Building Program and validation																															
T5.1 Venture Building Syllabus																															
T5.2 Selection of students for the validation phase																															
T5.3 Venture Building Program course and mentoring																															
T5.4 Venture Fellowship program																															
WP6 Venture Building Program refinement and mutual learning																															
T6.1 Establish guidelines and standard operating procedures in line with those adopted in the considered ENTREPRENEDU countries																														D6.2	
T6.2 Synergies of the project with other existing programs and initiatives																														D6.3	
T6.3 Business plan and related ENTREPRENEDU model exploitation																														D6.1	
WP7 Communication and dissemination																															
T7.1 Dissemination and communication strategy				D7.1																											
T7.2 Networking and dissemination activities																															

5.1 SCHEDULE MANAGEMENT

Schedule management is the process of ensuring that the quality of the project schedule is baselined, maintained, and managed. It is a dynamic process that occurs throughout the project lifecycle: under the rolling wave approach, as more information becomes available, the schedule can be refined to reflect the updated information. Schedule management is accomplished through a stringent change control process, and a comprehensive monitoring and reporting system. Project status was monitored against the baseline on a monthly basis, and the Work-Plan was updated as needed. The PM had primary responsibility for coordinating the gathering of schedule status information from all partners.

The project overall schedule management was the responsibility of the Project Coordinator; the schedule management within each WP was managed by the WPL; the

detailed action plan for each task was managed by the leader of that task; thus, the different schedule management processes were therefore managed by different people depending on the level.

As the monthly monitoring was performed, the PM had the opportunity to identify schedule slippage on critical paths tasks: the PM and the PC worked together to identify ways to get the project back on schedule.

For variances greater than 1 month, the PM could choose to ask guidance of the SC. Variances greater than 3 months were considered unacceptable. The PM and PC were to immediately inform the SC if they determined that any milestones were at risk of being missed.

If a change occurred, the PM was to incorporate proposed change(s) into an updated work-plan.

The approved schedule Plan was stored in the ENTREPRENEDU Google Drive repository, maintained by the PM and available to all project teams.

5.2 ACTION ITEM MANAGEMENT

Actionable activities were traced by the relevant minutes of meetings and teleconferences. Each action included the following information:

- action identifier;
- action responsible;
- action deadline.

Actions could have three different states, which depended on the current level of accomplishment:

- an action was IN PROGRESS if it had been initiated but was not yet managed;
- an action was DONE if there was evidence that somebody accomplished the action;
- an action was DELAYED if it was postponed with respect to the fixed date.

The PM was in charge of managing the project action items list, which was stored in the ENTREPRENEDU repository. The action item list was checked and discussed during plenary and technical teleconferences.

6 PROJECT BUDGET

To finance the project and ensure a high quality of performance and that all partners had access to a sufficient level of resources, the total budget of ENTREPRENEDU accounted for EUR 1,048,950.03, 100% EU granted over 30 months.

As specified in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, the financial contribution of the Funding Authority to the ENTREPRENEDU project was distributed by the Project Coordinator.

The coordinator had to distribute the payments between the beneficiaries without unjustified delay.

The following payments were made to the Coordinator:

- one pre-financing payment;
- one or more interim payments, on the basis of the request(s) for interim payment;
- one payment of the balance, on the basis of the request for payment of the balance.

The aim of the pre-financing was to provide the beneficiaries with a float. It remained the property of the EU until the payment of the balance. The Agency made the pre-financing payment to the coordinator 30 days from entry into force/10 days before starting date – whichever is the latest. An amount of EUR 52,447.50, corresponding to 5% of the maximum grant amount, was retained by the Agency from the initial pre-financing payment and transferred into the Mutual Insurance Mechanism (MIM). Interim and final payments were made subject to project deliverables. The consortium duly reported on the progress of ENTREPRENEDU project in accordance with the reporting calendar set out in the Grant Agreement.

The Agency will pay to the coordinator the amount due as final payment within 90 days from receiving the periodic report. The payment of the balance closes the financial aspects of the grant (partial payment for partially completed WPs possible) and releases the amount retained for the Mutual Insurance Mechanism.

ENTREPRENEDU foresees the following periodic reporting and payments:

Figure 2: Figure representing ENTREPRENEDU's reporting and payment schedule

Reporting					Payments	
Reporting periods			Type	Deadline	Type	Deadline (time to pay)
RP No	Month from	Month to				
					Initial prefinancing	30 days from entry into force/10 days before starting date – whichever is the latest
1	1	18	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
2	19	30	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Final payment	90 days from receiving periodic report

- Initial pre-financing: the aim of the pre-financing was to provide the beneficiaries with a float. It remained the property of the EU until the final payment. For initial prefinancings, the amount due, schedule and modalities are set out in the Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement.
- Interim payment: Interim payments reimbursed the eligible lump sum contributions claimed for work packages implemented during the reporting periods. Interim payments were made in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Data Sheet (see Point 4.2). Payment was subject to the approval of the periodic report and the work packages declared. The interim payment will be calculated by the granting authority in the following steps: Step 1 – Calculation of the total accepted EU contribution; Step 2 – Limit to the interim payment ceiling.
- Final payment: The final payment (payment of the balance) reimburses the remaining eligible lump sum contributions claimed for the implemented work packages. Final payments can also pay partially completed work packages. The final payment will be made in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement. Payment is subject to the approval of the final periodic report and the work packages declared. Their approval does not imply recognition of compliance, authenticity, completeness or correctness of their content. Work packages (or parts of them) that have not been delivered or cannot be approved will be rejected (see Article 27 of the

Grant Agreement). The final grant amount for the action will be calculated in the following steps: Step 1 – Calculation of the total accepted EU contribution.

More details can be found in the Consortium Agreement and in the Grant Agreement.

6.1 BUDGET/COST MANAGEMENT

ENTREPRENEDU was a lump-sum grant and, as such, the overall lump sum was fixed in the grant agreement. The breakdown of lump sum shares per beneficiary and per work package were included in the grant agreement (Annex 2). The detailed cost estimates from the ENTREPRENEDU proposal were not part of the grant agreement. Once the lump sum was fixed in the grant agreement, the costs actually incurred were not relevant.

This called for budget flexibility as follows: ENTREPRENEDU consortium members could use the budget as they saw fit as long as the project was implemented as agreed. The actual distribution of the lump sum was invisible to the EC. However, budget transfers required an amendment if the consortium wanted to reflect them in the grant agreement.

Transfers between Work Packages were possible if:

- Work Packages concerned were not already completed (and declared in a financial statement).
- Justified by the technical and scientific implementation of the action.

The reporting was done by using a standard reporting template. The coordinator declared work packages as “Completed” or “Not Completed”. This had to be justified by the technical periodic report. All work packages were completed as planned within the project duration. As such, there was no need to defer any work package to a subsequent reporting period or declare any as 'Partially Completed' in the final reporting. Completion was assessed based on the execution of the activities described in the Description of Action, regardless of specific outcomes.

The financial report was much simplified and, to a large extent, automated. The financial statement for all beneficiaries was automatically generated (based on the accepted work packages and the corresponding lump sum shares). The ‘use of resources’ report (certificates on financial statements) is not required for lump sum grants.

All work packages were completed as planned, and no deviations or amendments were required. Consequently, there was no need to apply the mechanisms foreseen for partially completed or rejected work packages. No observations or objections were raised by the Project Officer during the reporting process. As such, the full lump sums associated with each work package were deemed eligible based on the completion of the activities outlined in the Description of Action.

Below the summary of the dos and don'ts for financial reporting:

Figure 3: Figure representing dos and don'ts of financial reporting

Keeping records

7 RISK MANAGEMENT

In order to grant the quality of the project, ENTREPRENEDU recognised the importance of maximising the results of positive events and minimising the consequences of adverse events. For this purpose, risk management was key for a proper project quality management. According to the PMBOK® Guide, a risk is “an uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, has a positive or negative effect on one or more project objectives such as scope, schedule, cost, or quality”. For the purpose of this document, only uncertain events with a potential negative impact are considered. If the foreseen event or condition took place, it became an actual issue to be dealt with by the project’s Consortium. From this perspective, Risk Management

was the identification, assessment, and prioritisation of risks to minimise, monitor, and control the probability and/or impact of unfortunate events also known as threats. Since not all risks can be eliminated, mitigation strategies and contingency plans can be developed to lessen their impact if they occur. Essentially, effective risk management requires an informed understanding of relevant risks, an assessment of their relative priority and a rigorous approach to monitoring and controlling them. The responsibility of managing project risks relied upon the Coordinator: identified risks were tackled and alerts were raised in case any of the identified risks increased its priority. All activities related with the risk management were monitored by the PM with collaboration of each WP leader for specific issues relevant within every specific WP.

7.1 RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

The Risk Management activities were applied to the ENTREPRENEDU project to attempt to decrease the probability and impact of negative events by identifying and planning for risks before significant negative consequences occurred. This section described the process used to identify, classify, document, and track risks during the project. The risk management lifecycle consisted of the following steps, as shown below:

Figure 4: Figure representing the risk management lifecycle

These steps were executed in sequence for each project risk introduced in the risk management process. Each WPL developed a specific risk management plan for the WPs they were managing. These WP-specific risk management plans were rolled-up into a single risk management plan for the whole project. The most commonly used tool to record information about risks was the Risk Register, which acted as a central repository for all identified potential threats of the project. Prepared by the PM (with inputs from all members), the Risk Register was used to identify, classify, organise, evaluate, and track all levels of risks that may affect the project. Mitigation strategies

were then identified and tracked for implementation at appropriate times during the timeline of the project. The Risk Register was maintained by the Project Manager and was constantly updated as the project evolved. The most critical risks in the risk register were reviewed as a standing agenda item of the project's monthly plenary meetings. During these reviews, each risk was considered to see how it had changed since the last meeting, to monitor the status of risk mitigation measures, and to determine if any actions needed to be taken to further reduce the risk.

7.2 RISK IDENTIFICATION

Risk Identification is the proactive process of uncovering risks which might affect the project before they turn into problems. Risk identification is an iterative process. The first phase of risk identification occurred during the proposal phase of the project; the risks identified during the proposal phase were re-examined and updated based on the current state of the project, all throughout the lifecycle of the project. Participants in risk identification included subject-matter experts, WPLs, and project management and team members. Identified risks were documented in the risk register and discussed/reviewed during the monthly project meetings. Risks could span through various aspects including those that were political, design-related, procurement-related, environmental, technical, organisational, external, and/or economical. For ENTREPRENUEDU, two main categories were used, i.e. project-level risks and WP-level risks. Each time a new risk was detected, it was managed. Nevertheless, the biggest effort was put at the beginning in order to anticipate, as far as possible, the monitoring of possible risks, and plan, if the case, mitigation actions. Thanks to this proactive approach, no significant risks materialized during the course of the project.

7.3 RISK ANALYSIS, QUALIFICATION, AND PRIORITISATION

Risk Analysis was the most detailed phase of the entire risk management process. It involved evaluating and prioritising the risks. Evaluating a risk involved establishing values for its potential effect on scope, cost and/or schedule of the project. A determination was made as to the:

- probability (likelihood) of the risk occurring;
- ability to mitigate the risk;
- potential effect of the risk.

There were two primary methods for conducting risk analysis:

- qualitative: assessing the probability and impact of risks;
- quantitative: using mathematical methods to objectively assess the probability and impact of risks.

The determination of risk probability (likelihood of occurrence) and impact (degree of its effect) was a subjective process which considered the criticality of internal and external project factors within the specific context of the ENTREPRENEDU project. The probability and the impact for each identified risk were assessed using the following approach:

Probability

- Very Low – (<10%)
- Low – (10-29%)
- Medium – (30-50%)
- High – (51-70%)
- Very High – (>70%)

Impact

- Very High (Catastrophic) – Risk that has a catastrophic impact on project cost, schedule or performance.
- High (Major) – Risk that has a major impact on project cost, schedule or performance.
- Medium (Significant) – Risk that has the potential to significantly impact project cost, schedule or performance.
- Low (Minimal) – Risk that has relatively minimal impact on cost, schedule or performance.
- Very Low (Trivial) – Risk that has only a trivial impact on cost, schedule or performance.

The combination of probability and impact was used to evaluate the risk level (Low, Medium or High) and to get a list of the prioritised risks. The Impact and Probability matrix was then elaborated by assigning different colours to each risk:

1. **green** showed a low risk level;
2. **yellow** showed a medium risk level;
3. **red** showed a high risk level, which requires constant monitoring.

7.4 RISK RESPONSE PLANNING

Risk response is the process of deciding what should be done with a risk, if anything at all. Risk response answered two key questions:

- (1) who owned the risk (responsibility)
- (2) what could / was to be done (scope and actions).

Strategies and plans were developed to minimise the effects of a risk to a point where the risk could be controlled and managed. For each major risk, a risk response plan was developed. The range of response actions for the project was as follows:

1. Transfer: risk was external to the project. Resources and knowledge outside of the project were better able to manage the risk. Transfer implied the ultimate accountability, responsibility, and authority to expend resources, it required acceptance of the risk by the receiving party. Transferring liability for risk was most effective in dealing with financial risk exposure.
2. Accept: nothing was done, but handled the risk as an issue if it occurred. However, no further resources were expended in managing the risk. These were usually risks of lower significance.
3. Avoid: determined actions that, if executed enough in advance, would prevent the risk from occurring
4. Mitigate: eliminated or reduced the risk by reducing the impact, reducing the probability, or shifting the timeframe when action had to be taken.
5. Watch: monitored the risks for early warning of critical changes in impact, probability, timeframe or other aspects.
6. Contingency: determined actions that were executed once the risk had occurred to address the situation (actions taken especially to minimise adverse consequences).

For all identified risks, the various handling techniques should be evaluated in terms of feasibility, expected effectiveness, cost, and schedule implications, and the effect on the system's technical quality and performance. The Project Manager, together with the concerned WP and Task Leaders, is responsible for developing and evaluating different risk handling strategies that are best fitted to the project's circumstances. The Project Manager is also responsible for monitoring and controlling the performance of risk handling actions.

7.5 RISK MONITORING AND CONTROL

Risk Monitoring was the process of keeping track of the risks and evaluating the effectiveness of the response actions. Monitoring could also provide a basis for developing additional response actions and identifying new risks, and was done in a continuous manner. The level of critical risks on the ENTREPRENEDU project was tracked, monitored, and reported regularly, with specific discussions during the monthly meetings' calls. As more risks were identified, they were qualified and added to the risk management strategy to ensure they were monitored at the appropriate times and adequate response strategies were developed. During risk monitoring and control, the following tasks were performed:

1. identifying, analysing, and planning for new risks;
2. reviewing project performance information (such as progress/status reports, issues, and corrective actions);
3. re-analysing existing risks to see if the probability, impact, or proper response plan had changed;
4. reviewing the execution of risk responses and analysing their effectiveness;
5. reviewing the effectiveness of the risk process to determine whether changes to the approach, tools or techniques were required.

7.6 ENTREPRENEDU CRITICAL RISKS IDENTIFICATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

The ENTREPRENEDU Critical risks identification and risk management strategy has already been implemented by and it is reported here:

Table 5: Table representing ENTREPRENEDU's critical risk identification and risk management strategy

Description of risk (Low/Medium/High)	WPs involved	Risk-Mitigation Measures and Outcomes
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Lack of overall coordination Likelihood: low Happened: No	WP1	Effective coordination has been ensured by the managerial structure and the project work plan. In particular, a Steering Committee composed of WP leaders was established and met every 6 months or when convened by the Coordinator. Reporting and communication activities were implemented as planned, along with the elaboration of a Data Management Plan and a Quality Assurance Plan. Although contingency measures were in place to address unforeseen events—such as the possibility for experienced staff at the coordinating organisation or partner organisations to take over coordination tasks—they were ultimately not needed, as no such risks materialized during the project.
Consortium disruption Likelihood: low Happened: No	WP1	All partners have extensive experience and proven track records in managing large-scale projects at international, European, national, and local levels. While contingency measures were in place to address potential issues related to partner engagement or performance, these risks did not materialize. All partners remained actively committed throughout the project, working collaboratively toward the shared objectives, which they continue to regard as a strategic tool for fostering innovation and enhancing the competitiveness of both the entrepreneurial and educational ecosystems.
Conflicts in the Consortium Likelihood: low Happened: No	WP1	A comprehensive Consortium Agreement has been formulated by all partners. The PM will follow strict administrative guidelines and implement actions against partners failing to comply with procedures agreed upon in the CA. The PM will maintain an easily searchable record of all relevant correspondence among partners. All partners have a track record of solving emergent problems in a collegial spirit.
Delays in deliverables Likelihood: medium Happened: No	All WPs	A comprehensive Consortium Agreement was formulated and agreed upon by all partners. The Project Manager followed strict administrative guidelines and was prepared to implement corrective actions in case of non-compliance with the procedures outlined in the Agreement. A searchable record of all relevant correspondence among partners was maintained throughout the project. While these measures were in place to address potential issues, they were not required, as all partners demonstrated strong cooperation and resolved any emerging matters in a collegial and constructive spirit.

<p>A partner leaves the project Likelihood: low Happened: No</p>	<p>All WPs</p>	<p>Partners' expectations were continuously monitored to ensure sustained commitment throughout the project. The overall project management and coordination structure, as outlined in WP1, was designed to address potential disengagement or misalignment. While contingency measures were in place—such as substituting a partner with another of similar profile or redistributing tasks among the many capable partners—these options were never needed. All partners remained engaged and committed, allowing the project to progress smoothly without requiring structural adjustments.</p>
<p>The website/platform is not evolving at the same speed as the project Likelihood: medium Happened: No</p>	<p>WP4, WP6, WP3, WP5, WP7</p>	<p>ENTREPRENEDU included the development of a dedicated Dissemination and Communication Plan, which was regularly reviewed and updated throughout the project. The experience and expertise of F6S, the partner responsible for communication and dissemination, ensured smooth implementation and avoided any major issues. In addition, the competence and support of the other partners provided valuable backup and reinforcement when needed. However, no critical challenges arose. All partners actively contributed to promotional efforts, leveraging their strong social media presence—each with at least three active accounts on different platforms—and regularly creating and sharing targeted content aligned with the project's objectives and evolving needs.</p>
<p>Low participants to the Hackathon Likelihood: medium Happened: No</p>	<p>WP3, WP7</p>	<p>Specific efforts were successfully carried out to promote the project during its initial phase and in the lead-up to each Hackathon. The consortium leveraged its collective experience to reach higher education institutions and start-ups, using social media, the F6S platform, and the networks of all supporting organisations. Local communities within each partner's network were actively engaged from the outset through dedicated launch events promoting ENTREPRENEDU. Fondazione E. Amaldi and Corallia, with their direct experience in organising Hackathons such as the EC-promoted CASSINI Hackathons and ActInSpace, effectively mobilised their networks of institutions, entrepreneurs, students, and relevant target groups. EBAN contributed its expertise in business and investment events and activated its extensive international network. Most partners also benefited from established links with universities or research centres. The Dissemination and Communication Plan supported the continuous monitoring and strategic adaptation of outreach activities, which ensured strong participation and visibility without encountering major obstacles.</p>

<p>The website/platform to launch the call doesn't work. Likelihood: low Happened: No</p>	<p>WP4, WP6, WP3, WP5, WP7</p>	<p>The experience and expertise of F6S ensured the smooth operation of the website/platform used to launch calls to action and support project activities. Although contingency measures were in place from the start—such as identifying alternative platforms to ensure continuity in stakeholder engagement—no disruptions occurred. The proactive approach of all partners in scouting backup options from the beginning further strengthened the project's resilience, even though these measures were ultimately not required.</p>
<p>Difficulty to engage external evaluators for the proposals Likelihood: medium Happened: No</p>	<p>WP3, WP5</p>	<p>The task leader responsible for engaging external evaluators identified potential professionals early on through their existing network. In addition, the task on Stakeholder and Linked Initiatives Engagement was activated at the start of the project to attract experts across relevant areas. These experts were evaluated and validated collectively by all partners. Thanks to this proactive approach, the engagement process proceeded smoothly, and no issues or delays occurred.</p>
<p>Prolonged and costly evaluation process. Likelihood: low Happened: No</p>	<p>WP3</p>	<p>The evaluation process was closely monitored throughout the project, allowing for the early detection of potential issues. Although the contracts with external evaluators were designed to be flexible—enabling the adjustment of workloads based on performance—such corrective measures were ultimately not necessary. The evaluation activities proceeded as planned, with all evaluators performing effectively and no major problems arising.</p>
<p>IPR issues not sorted Likelihood: medium Happened: No</p>	<p>WP3, WP4, WP5</p>	<p>IPR issues related to the project were limited, as the exploitation model was based on the openness of the project's processes. A first draft of the Data Management Plan (DMP) was produced on schedule at M3 and regularly updated throughout the project. The final release of the DMP was completed at M30. No significant IPR-related challenges emerged, confirming the effectiveness of the open approach and the planned mitigation measures.</p>

8 PROJECT COMMUNICATION

Properly communicating on a project is a critical success factor for managing the expectations of the project consortium and the European Commission. The Project Coordinator was responsible for communication between the Project and the EC. The

ENTREPRENEDU project used several mechanisms for ensuring open and frequent communications amongst its members:

1. electronic mails (e-mail) and mailing lists;
2. conference calls;
3. face-to-face meetings.

8.1 ELECTRONIC MAILS AND MAILING LIST

E-mail was the main means of interpersonal communication in ENTREPRENEDU. It was used for information exchanges, meeting minutes, and executive summaries. As an informal and rapid tool, it proved well-suited for non-critical communications. E-mail distribution lists were maintained and regularly updated by Fondazione E. Amaldi and made available to all partners. Any changes concerning people involved or contact details were communicated to Fondazione E. Amaldi in a timely manner.

The following rules ensured the appropriate use of e-mail communication among project participants:

- Messages were addressed only to the relevant parties; recipients avoided copying all partners unnecessarily and used ‘reply all’ with caution.
- Subject lines were made explicit and clear. Mailing list addresses automatically appended the [ENTREPRENEDU] tag to subject lines, and users were encouraged to include informative subject headings (e.g., “Meeting minutes 2016-03-17”).
- Attachments were generally avoided. When necessary, files were compressed into ZIP format, but the preferred method was to upload documents to the shared ENTREPRENEDU Google Drive and share the corresponding link. This prevented issues with email size limits and avoided exceeding mailbox quotas, especially when partners were out of office.

E-mail exchanges were consistently used by project partners to share information, proposals, and ideas, and to coordinate the preparation of deliverables and other outputs such as papers, presentations, and reports to the European Commission.

All mailing lists were managed by Fondazione E. Amaldi. Requests to add or remove members from project mailing lists were addressed directly to them.

8.2 CONFERENCE CALLS

Videoconferences and teleconferences were scheduled at least one week in advance and followed a defined agenda. Google Meet was the platform used for these meetings. Telephone was used when fast responses, personal interaction, or reliable confirmation were required. For urgent matters, phone calls proved effective, and up-to-date contact numbers were made available to all partners. To ensure clarity and avoid misunderstandings, it was standard practice to follow up phone conversations with a summary email.

Regularly scheduled conference calls served as the primary channel for in-depth communication among WP leaders, work package members, and deliverable teams. Project plenary calls were held monthly to ensure coordination across all work packages, share updates on activities, and discuss any emerging issues or developments. In addition to plenary meetings, technical calls were held bi-weekly to support integration across the different work packages. A fixed schedule was agreed upon to streamline participation: the last Thursday of each month at 3:00 PM CET (Rome time). Meetings could be rescheduled if needed, according to consortium needs.

Each partner organisation was expected to ensure the participation of at least one representative in these meetings. WP leaders coordinated their teams through additional calls when needed, proposing them with at least one week's notice. Formal discussions among WP leaders were also held regularly to maintain alignment and ensure mutual support across WPs.

Minutes of each conference call were prepared immediately after the meeting in a schematic format, outlining key decisions and action points. These minutes were made available to all partners for consultation and were stored in the shared ENTREPRENEDU repository on Google Drive.

8.3 MEETINGS

ENTREPRENEDU identified the following categories of meetings:

- Monthly meetings with PC, PM, and WPL. Online meetings, starting in February 2023, fixed date and timing (1h or more according to the consortium's needs) agreed by the whole consortium, happen every last Thursday of the month at 3:00 pm CET, unless agreed otherwise.

- General Assembly meetings with SC. In person meetings, every 6 months (twice a year), if possible in conjunction with local events and academies organisation.

Sometimes, WP specific meetings were held, on the basis of requests from partners and according to implementation needs. These extraordinary meetings helped finalize smooth WP implementation.

Below a schedule for all the monthly meetings that took place within the project:

Project Monthly Meetings

Monthly Meeting #1	24/02/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #2	30/03/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #3	27/04/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #4	31/05/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #5	26/06/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #6	27/07/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #7	07/09/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #8	26/10/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #9	01/12/23	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #10	24/01/2024	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #11	29/02/24	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #12	24/04/2024	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #13	30/05/2024	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #14	27/06/2024	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #15	26/07/2024	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #16	05/09/2024	15:00 CET

Monthly Meeting #17	31/10/2024	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #18	28/11/2024	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #19	19/12/2024	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #20	28/02/2025	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #21	27/03/2025	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #22	30/04/2025	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #23	29/05/2025	15:00 CET
Monthly Meeting #24	26/06/2025	15:00 CET

General Assemblies schedule

1. 30.01-01.02.2023: in Rome during the k.o.
2. 14.06.2023: In Rimini, Italy.
3. 20.12.2023: Online.
4. 27.03.2024: In Sofia, Bulgaria.
5. 16.01.2025: Online.

8.4 ENTREPRENEDU PROJECT WEBSITE

The ENTREPRENEDU project website (<https://entreprenedu.eu/>) served as one of the main tools for disseminating information about the consortium and the project's achievements. It provided visitors with comprehensive information about the project's context, objectives, activities, and results.

The website was developed in English and included direct access to ENTREPRENEDU's social media accounts via the homepage. It also featured a Public Documents area, where downloadable materials—such as project reports, publicity content, and relevant publications—were made available. The website played a key role in engaging external stakeholders, promoting events, and sharing academic papers and other content produced by the project team.

The website was developed and regularly updated by F6S throughout the project. For further details, including strategic use and updates of the website, refer to the final version of project deliverable D7.1 – Dissemination and Communication Plan.

8.5 DOCUMENT REPOSITORY

As a primary tool to facilitate information exchange, a shared web-based collaborative environment was established and used throughout the project. This environment functioned as a project tracking system accessible to all partners, ensuring that information and documentation were easily available and kept up to date with minimal effort.

A dedicated Google Drive repository was created for the ENTREPRENEDU project, serving as the central hub for all documents generated during the project's lifetime. Google Drive allowed partners to store, share, and collaboratively edit files—such as documents, spreadsheets, and presentations—in real time.

In addition to serving as a repository, the Drive provided a functional workspace for day-to-day collaboration. A structured folder system was set up and shared with designated representatives from each partner organisation. Any requests for access were managed by the Project Coordinator.

Documents were uploaded to their respective folders using clear and descriptive file names to ensure easy navigation and understanding for all users. The platform's revision history feature allowed for the recovery of earlier versions and accidentally deleted files directly through the web interface or from synced devices. Documents were stored in various editable formats to support collaborative work across the consortium.

8.6 ENTREPRENEDU PROJECT TEMPLATES

To ensure consistency in the ENTREPRENEDU project, when communicating with external stakeholders or interested parties, a set of standard templates for various communications activities were developed. These templates include:

1. Deliverable template standard
2. PowerPoint presentation template
3. Press release template
4. Certificate of participation template
5. Standard logos for the project

8.7 ENTREPRENEDU SHARED CALENDAR

A Google Calendar specifically created for the ENTREPRENEDU project was shared among all partners. While it was accessible to all, in practice it was primarily managed by the Project Coordinator and Project Manager, who handled the scheduling of meetings, sending of invitations, and management of key deadlines.

The calendar proved useful in:

- A. sharing project timelines with all team members
- B. organising meetings and keeping partners informed
- C. sending automatic reminders for upcoming appointments
- D. centralising deadline management in a single, accessible space

9 PROJECT REPORTING

Each partner generated an internal technical report for each work package (WP), edited annually by the respective WP Leader (WPL) and collected by the Project Manager (PM). The Project Coordinator (PC) was informed in case of any inconsistencies or unexpected resource management. All partners remained committed to providing the PM with the necessary information and documentation required to prepare the official reports submitted to the European Commission.

The reporting covered the technical progress of the project, the results achieved (e.g., deliverables), compliance with the work programme, and all relevant management information, including resource use, costs, and any delays. The PC consolidated this input to provide an overall synthesis of the project status and compiled the required reports for submission.

The following reports were prepared and officially submitted by the PC:

- Periodic Report (submitted in M18), including:
 - an interim technical report summarising the results and their exploitation and dissemination
 - any other information requested by the Project Officer
- Final Activity Report (submitted in M30), including:
 - a final technical report with a publishable summary, covering the project results, their exploitation and dissemination, conclusions, and socio-economic impact

- a final financial report including a summary financial statement generated by the EU portal, consolidating the individual financial statements of all partners and including the final payment request

The PC submitted the final report within the required 60 days following the end of the reporting period. Regular review meetings were also held to update both the European Commission and the Consortium on the status of the project and to ensure alignment with expected outcomes.

10 CHANGE MANAGEMENT

Change management in ENTREPRENEDU referred to the structured process used to assess, approve, implement, and track changes to agreed specifications and baselines. It ensured that configured items were always maintained in a known, approved state, and that only validated and authorised modifications were applied throughout the project lifecycle.

The ENTREPRENEDU change management process defined the procedures for managing changes in scope, policies, processes, plans, or schedules. Change requests could be made to expand or reduce the project scope or revise operational elements.

A multi-level approval process was used depending on the nature and impact of each request:

- The **Project Manager** was authorised to analyse and approve changes with little or no impact on scope, budget, schedule, or project risk.
- Changes with low to moderate impact were forwarded to the **Project Coordinator (PC)** for review.
- Requests resulting in significant changes to scope, schedule, or budget were escalated to the **Steering Committee (SC)**, which made final decisions based on analysis provided by the PM and input from the PC.

Each change request was tracked from initiation to closure through the following stages:

1. **Identify** – The required change was documented.

2. **Validate** – The change was reviewed to confirm it warranted management attention.
3. **Analyse** – The potential impact on schedule, cost, and effort was assessed.
4. **Control** – A decision was made on whether to implement the change.
5. **Action** – Approved changes were implemented, including updates to project plans if needed.
6. **Close** – Completion was verified and the change request formally closed.

Throughout the project, this structured approach ensured effective change tracking and decision-making. In practice, the number of major change requests was limited, and no significant disruptions arose, confirming the robustness of the original planning and the effectiveness of the change management process.

10.1 DOCUMENT CHANGE PROCESS

The reason for any change—whether a correction or an enhancement—to project documents was clearly documented in the change history section of each document. Change justifications were explicitly stated, and significant modifications were listed with corresponding page numbers to ensure that updates could be easily identified and compared with previous versions.

Upon receiving a change request, the responsible person and/or the relevant Work Package Leader analysed its potential impact on the specific deliverable and on other project outcomes. When necessary, they consulted with the Project Coordinator. Following this evaluation, the change request was either approved or disapproved. The editor communicated the outcome of the evaluation to the originator of the request and to all relevant partners. In cases where the change was disapproved, the editor provided a written explanation within the change request form, which sometimes led to further discussion before reaching a final accept or reject decision. If the change was approved, the editor implemented the necessary modifications and issued a new draft version of the deliverable for review and final approval or release. This structured and transparent process ensured consistent document quality and traceability across the project.

11 CONCLUSIONS

This document presents the final approach taken by the ENTREPRENEDU team to manage the quality of project implementation. As Deliverable D1.6 – “Quality Assurance Plan – Final Release”, it reflects the consolidated framework and practices that ensured the project adhered to the original work plan while maintaining a high standard of quality.

It summarises the tools and procedures used to manage the project, facilitate internal and external communication, and monitor quality and risks throughout the project lifecycle. These mechanisms were continuously refined as the project progressed, ensuring responsiveness to emerging needs and challenges.

Initially conceived as a living document, the Quality Assurance Plan evolved alongside the project. This final release integrates all updates made during implementation and captures the matured quality management strategy adopted by the consortium.